

Appendix 2

This appendix describes the traits of direct and indirect characteristics that are possible to obtain during the digitization of the first forest parcels' land register maps. The main objective is to methodically describe the observable phenomena, correctly interpret them and create an easy-to-navigate manual to be used as a tool for research of similar nature. Visualization of forest parcels, prepared according to this methodology, is available in Appendix 3.

A Direct characteristics

A.1 Forest toponymy

The first step is to identify the respective forest parcel in the land register. Digitized index sketches generally contain an overview diagram of the tracts that are present in the cadastre (*Riege Croquis*), usually also with their name list (*Verzeichnis der Riede*). The visuals of the overview diagram generally have a neutral colour, and the borders of the forest tracts are marked with red; similar design of marking tract borders is employed in the parcel map detail as well. In some cases, the tracts can be colour-coded with grey in the overview map sketch. Each tract is marked with a letter and has its own unique toponym (fig. 1A).

Figure 1A: Schematic representation of the mapped area of the Haluzice cadastre (sign. 634), made in 1828 by the surveyor Josef Halm. Cadastral tracts are marked with red lines and labelled with Roman numerals, while the tract toponyms are listed in the table on the left. Published with permission of Moravian Provincial Archives.

The toponyms were written in German or eventually in a Germanized variation regardless of the contemporary grammatical rules of the respective country's language. The toponyms were recorded by the surveyor in close coordination with local residents, and it is assumed that the area in question was widely known under the documented names, as they served as geographical identifiers within the cadastre. In case of a forest, many toponyms including tree species specifications can be found (oak grove, beech forest, firwood), terrain features (pits, deep ruts, floodplains), hunting facilities (wolf pits, game preserve, pheasantry), or problematic property relations (such as disputes, land with prohibited access or management or with fraudulent claims). Each forest toponym is crucial for cross-referencing with other sources, provided it has not undergone significant changes. From the available large-scale map materials, it is possible to verify whether the currently used toponym is identical or not. Toponyms represent unique information and can be recorded in a database either a) in their original transcription (see Appendix 3) or b) in a phonetically adjusted form according to the current grammar of the national language.

A.2 Ownership structure

Each forest parcel was registered with a name of the owner. Property owners could then be identified based on the following: (i) family name (dominion forest), (ii) the name and house number (rustic forests), (iii) the name of the relevant municipality (for municipal or urban forests), or (iv) the name of a religious organization (for episcopal forests, forests of religious orders, or parish forests). The categories of owners are listed in Table 1A.

Table 1A: Ownership categories

Category	Description
Dominion forest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forests owned by aristocracy; generally the most common kind of property ownership. Such forest parcels have an area of several units to tens of hectares. • General notation pattern: <i>Family name – Noble title – First name – Estate name</i>. • Described in German or marked with “D” in case of smaller parcels (from the Latin <i>dominium</i>). • E.g.: <i>Illesházy Graf Stephan als Herrschaft Brumow</i>
Rustic forest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest owned by small landowners, long-time settlers – peasants; the forest parcels range in size from fractions to a few hectares. • General notation pattern: <i>Last and first name (or names) – House number (numbers)</i>. • Czech names were noted in German transcription and house number is marked with “N” (from German <i>die Nummer</i>). In case of very small parcels, only the number/s is/are noted. • E.g.: <i>Kosubik Johann N 27</i>.
Municipal forest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest owned by a municipality; generally on the land of one cadastre only. The size of parcels varied, most often in several units to lower tens of hectares.

Category	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General notation pattern: <i>Municipality name</i> – “municipality” in German (<i>Gemeinde</i>). • Czech name in German transcription; in smaller parcels only the letter “G” (from German <i>Gemeinde</i>). • E.g.: <i>Wlachowitz Gemeinde</i>.
Episcopal forest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest owned by a religious (arch)diocese, chapter, order (monastery), or parish forests; the size of the parcels is highly variable, most commonly ranging from a few hectares to lower tens of hectares (similar to municipal forests). • General notation pattern: <i>Religious subject</i> – <i>Location</i>. • Name in German, inconsistent form of notation. • E.g.: <i>Pfaar August</i>

Disputable ownerships have also been recorded – such cases involved more parties who claimed the property, or when the property already belonged to more than one subject. It was common to witness joint ownership, mostly in rustic forests. Less common were cases of owning both dominion and municipal parcel, or municipal and episcopal parcel.

Figure 2A: Examples of ownership notations in index sketches: a) dominion forests in Brumov cadastre (sign. 240), b) rustic forests in Nedašov (sign. 1642), c) municipal forests in Vlachovice (2929) and d) parish forest parcel (Pfaar August) in Újezd u Valašských Klobouk (sign. 1882). Published with permission of Moravian Provincial Archives.

A.3 *Tree species composition*

The prevalent tree species composition in the given forest parcels is a) noted using visual symbols, b) noted using abbreviations of German terminology, or c) indicated by a combination of both.

The symbols represent the tree habitus (coniferous or deciduous trees), and their size corresponds to the growth phase (young forest stands are represented by small saplings, while mature stands are shown with large trees). The symbols are chosen based on the size of the parcel and are repeated if the boundary of the forest tract (parcel) is depicted on multiple sheets. For smaller or narrower parcels, a written abbreviation is provided. The types of forest based on the prevalent tree species composition are listed in Table 2A.

Table 2A: Forest types by prevalent tree species

Category	Description
Deciduous forest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest predominantly consisting of one or more species of deciduous trees. • Visual symbol: a tree habitus of variable shape with spherical, oval, or distinctly elongated crown, drawn in black ink. More individuals, creating stands, are often depicted. • Textual note: the word <i>Laub</i>. Or the letter “L” (from German <i>Laubholz</i>).
Coniferous forest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest predominantly consisting of one or more coniferous tree species. • Visual symbol: a shape-variable tree habitus of triangular or pyramid crown drawn in black ink; individual branches are differentiated in various heights on the trunk. Usually depicted in clusters. • Textual note: the word <i>Nadl.</i> or the letter “N” (from German <i>Nadelholz</i>).
Mixed forest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest with both coniferous and deciduous (mixed) tree species composition. • Visual symbol: a tree habitus of variable shape with spherical, oval, or distinctly elongated crown, and a shape-variable tree habitus of triangular or pyramid crown with individual branches visible in various heights on the trunk. Drawn in black ink. In the basic form, a duo of a deciduous and a coniferous tree is depicted. • Textual note: the words <i>Laub. und Nadl.</i> or the letters “LN” (from German <i>Laub- und Nadelholz</i>).

There is no evidence on the specific tree species in the visuals of the index sketches – these data can, however, be obtained from appraisal registers which, among others, also contain groundwork management recommendations.

Figure 3A: Examples of tree habitus notation in the index sketches: a) young deciduous forest (Laub. J.M.) in Vlachovice cadastre (sign. 2929), b) mixed forest in Vysoké Pole cadastre (sign. 3000), c) medium coniferous forest (N. M. H.) in Študlov cadastre (sign. 2590). Published with permission of Moravian Provincial Archives.

A.4 Age structure

Age structure in parcels is noted in the following ways: a) a visual symbol and/or b) textual abbreviation. The visual symbol depicts trees (deciduous or coniferous) in different heights, i.e. ages. Forest age structure, or rather forest growth differentiation, seems to have been commonly implemented in the records for the purposes of forest management. Growth stages, defined in the contemporary literature in intervals, might give us an approximate on the time of the forest's inception. This information can be obtained by subtracting the lower and the upper stage growth interval limit from the date of creation of the respective index sketch. Growth stages and their rough definitions are given in Table 3A.

Table 3A: Growth stages and their framework definitions

Growth stage name	Abbreviation	Age interval		Characteristics
		Deciduous forest	Coniferous forest	
<i>Jungmais</i>	J.M.	0–30	0–24	Natural seedlings; young stands
<i>Stangenholz</i>	S.H.	30–60	25–54	Pole stands
<i>Mittelholz</i>	M.H.	60–80	55–75	Upcoming pole timber; pole timber
<i>Hochstämmig schlagbar</i>	H.S.	80–100	over 75	Harvest-mature, or overmature pole timber designated for logging

Figure 4A: Examples of growth stages' notation in the index sketches; a) young deciduous forest (J. M.) in Újezd U Valašských Klobouk cadastre (sign. 1882); b) coniferous pole stands (S. H.) in Lačnov cadastre (sign. 1214); c) deciduous medium-grown forest in Štítná nad Vláří cadaster (sign. 2543); d) coniferous forests ready for felling (Nadl. H. S.) in Tichov cadastre (sign. 362). Published with permission of Moravian Provincial Archives.

Each parcel in a forest that was managed in accordance with a certain management plan had been, according to § 257 in 1824 instructions, registered with one or, in some instances, two growth stages. For example, a notation of J.M.:M.H. growth stages can be (using forestry terminology) interpreted as a two-floor forest, i.e., the rejuvenated (younger) stands (J.M.) were growing under the canopy of the older trees (M.H.). Contemporary literature, however, does not provide information on differentiating growth stages in case of mixed stands. Forest parcels that did not meet the conditions of § 270 did not include this information and, after the issuing of the 1865 instructions, this parameter ceased to be recorded in the sketches of later creation date.

B Indirect characteristics

General characteristics that cannot be obtained or inferred from the index sketches but can be obtained from geoinformation systems after the digitization of the respective forest parcels.

B.1 Forest acreage

Forest area represents a quantitative trait informing about the size of the forest parcel in area units. At the time the index sketches were created, a metric system different from the current decimal system was used. The parcel area can be calculated using tools in geographic information systems in any unit, with hectares, commonly used in forestry, being recommended.

B.2 Environmental characteristics

Environmental characteristics represent a spectrum of derived information on qualitative and quantitative traits of the specific, geographically defined location of the forest parcel. These characteristics can be obtained using raster geospatial analysis on the base layer of digital terrain model. For basics, it is possible to calculate altitude, slope incline and aspect. Besides that, a range of morphological indices can be employed (e.g. Terrain Ruggedness Index, Terrain Wetness Index, etc.). The detected site characteristics can be used, in combination with e.g. historical records, for a more complex understanding of the place a forest has in landscape and its importance. An example can be the dependence of tree species composition on altitude; the impact of slope incline (making logging and transport harder) on the age of the stands or the recorded management form and tree species composition.